

A Comparative Study of Machine Learning and Transfer Learning Approaches to Vocal Biomarker Detection in Parkinson's Disease

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Abstract— Parkinson's disease (PD) affects speech in up to 90% of patients, making voice a promising biomarker for early, non-invasive screening. In this study, we benchmark voice-based classification frameworks for PD detection across three tiers: classical machine learning (ML) on handcrafted acoustic features, ensemble learning, and transfer learning with convolutional neural networks (CNNs) on spectrograms. Classical ML models with feature selection achieved strong results when age was included as a predictor, but performance collapsed when age was excluded, revealing a critical demographic bias. Ensemble methods offered minimal improvements but suffered from instability and high variance. Transfer learning with MobileNetV2 outperformed traditional approaches in capturing discriminative speech patterns, achieving a best run of 0.896 AUC score. These results emphasize both the potential and limitations of existing methods, reinforcing the need for transparent evaluation to achieve reliable and clinically relevant outcomes.

Keywords— Parkinson's Disease, Speech Analysis, Machine Learning, Acoustic Features, Transfer Learning, Spectrograms, MobileNetV2

I. INTRODUCTION

Voice is a rich medium of physiological information, encoding markers of neurological health within its acoustic properties. As a result, voice analysis has emerged as a promising modality for health-related detection tasks.

Parkinson's disease (PD) is the second most common neurodegenerative disease in the world [1]. While motor symptoms remain its defining clinical feature, speech impairments affect 90% of PD patients, resulting in a range of symptoms including hypophonia (reduced volume), monopitch, and tremors [2] [3]. These vocal impairments emerge early in the disease's progression, presenting an opportunity for non-invasive, cost-effective, and widely deployable screening tools [4].

A. Machine Learning for Voice-Based PD Detection

The advancement in machine learning (ML) has facilitated the exploration of PD detection through voice analysis. A study by Little et al. [5] demonstrated the viability of using handcrafted acoustic features paired with classical ML algorithms such as Support Vector Machines (SVMs), achieving a high classification accuracy of 91.4%. This work established a foundational framework that has

been extensively replicated and refined, adopting the same pipeline which typically involved predefined acoustic descriptors (e.g. jitter, shimmer, harmonics-to-noise ratio).

However, such approaches are inherently constrained by the representational capacity of handcrafted features, which may fail to capture subtle or complex pathological patterns. To overcome this, researches turned to deep learning (DL) methods, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) applied to spectrograms and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) for sequential modelling [6][7].

These architectures allow end-to-end learning directly from raw, or minimally processed audio signals.

Reported results of such methods are remarkable. Some CNN-based systems achieve over 95% accuracy. A paper by Worasawte et al. [8] achieved a 99% accuracy using VGGNet-16 (a multi-layer CNN system).

B. Methodological Challenges

Despite the promising results, a critical examination of the literature reveals a significant gap between reported performance and clinical applicability. This discrepancy is largely attributed to some methodological limitations. Datasets are often demographically imbalanced (age skewedness is a recurrent theme) and are subject to data leakage, particularly when multiple samples by the same subject are split across training and test sets. Under these conditions, models risk memorizing speaker-specific characteristics rather than learning to generalize true pathological markers, leading to inflated performance metrics and over-optimistic results [9][10].

C. Present Study

In this study, we treat Parkinson's detection as a case study for designing and evaluating technical frameworks for voice-based classification. We systematically compare classical ML models trained on handcrafted features with ensemble methods and transfer learning model using MobileNetV2 (CNNs trained on image processing tasks).

Our goal is to establish a transparent and reproducible framework for benchmarking voice-based ML systems. By grounding our experiments in PD, we aim to build insights that can be generalized to a broader class of health-related voice applications.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this paper, we offer a study using three methods: A machine learning, feature-based approach, an ML ensemble approach, and a deep learning (transfer learning) approach to PD pathology classification.

For the ML method, we test six classical ML algorithms: Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbours (kNN), Random Forest (RF), XGBoost (XGB), and Gradient Boosting (GB).

For base models (weak learners) we use four feature selection techniques to explore feature-relevance and model performance. These techniques are Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Filter-Based Feature Selection, Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE), and Minimum Redundancy Maximum Relevance (mRMR).

We use the previous base models with their best-performing feature-selected set to form three ensemble models: Soft Voting Ensemble Classifier (SVEC), Hard Voting Ensemble Classifier (HVEC), and Stacking Classifier and compare the result of each. Fig. 1 illustrates the generic process implemented for the ML half of this study. It demonstrates the workflow from raw data processing to the evaluation of the final ensemble models.

For the DL method we utilize pretrained CNNs through MobileNetV2 (trained on ImageNet) and train them on our data after transforming raw audio into time-frequency spectrograms.

In the following subsections we introduce the dataset used in this study, the features extracted from the voice signal, and different techniques compared under different conditions.

A. Dataset

This study used a publicly available dataset originally collected and published by Prior et al. [11]. The dataset

Fig. 1. Proposed machine learning methodology

consists of 81 distinct voice recordings of sustained /a/ phonation, 41 of which were taken from healthy patients (healthy control), the other 40 taken from clinically-confirmed patients diagnosed with PD (PwPD). A summary of participant demographics is provided in Table I [12].

TABLE I. DEMOGRAPHICS OF DATASET. TABLE BY IYER ET AL. [12]

	Healthy control (n=41)	Parkinson's disease (n=40)
Sex (M/F)	16/24	21/19
Age (years)	47.9 ± 14.5	66.6 ± 9.0
Disease duration (years)	-	9.5 ± 6.0

B. Feature Extraction

Acoustic feature extraction was performed using the OpenSMILE (open-source Media Interpretation by Large feature-space Extraction) framework through its Python library, opensmile (v. 2.6.0.1) [13].

We utilized the Geneva Minimalistic Acoustic Parameter Set (GeMAPS) version 01b [14] to obtain a standardized set of clinical features for voice pathology, configured on the functionals level. This resulted in 63 distinct features for each sample, covering frequency, amplitude, spectral, and temporal properties of the voice signal.

Feature correlation was assessed using Pearson Correlation to evaluate redundancy and inter-feature relationships. As illustrated in the correlation heatmap Fig. 2, the majority of feature pairs demonstrated low to moderate correlation, which indicates that the feature set is largely free from linear dependencies. This mitigates the issue of multicollinearity for linear models ensuring a more stable performance. It also suggests that the feature space is non-redundant, with most features providing unique information which helps prevent overfitting.

It's worth noting that Pearson correlation only captures linear relationships. This suggests the potential for significant non-linear relationships between features, which in turn underlines the importance of using tree-based models which are inherently capable of identifying such complex, non-linear interactions.

Fig. 2. Pearson correlation heatmap of feature set.

C. Machine Learning Models and Evaluation

We chose a set of six different machine learning algorithms to get a full picture of what works best. This selection covers both linear and non-linear methods, including baseline classifiers and advanced ensemble learners.

1) *Machine Learning Algorithms*: The following algorithms were implemented using the scikit-learn (v.1.6.1) and XGBoost (v.3.0.4) libraries in Python:

- **Logistic Regression (LR)**: A simple, reliable linear classification model. It offers a great starting point, and a baseline to compare to. It models the probability of class membership using the sigmoid function.

- **Support Vector Machine (SVM)**: A margin-based classifier that identifies the optimal hyperplane to separate classes. It uses kernels to draw linear or non-linear decision boundaries.

- **k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN)**: An instance-based learning method that classifies new samples according to the majority label of their closest neighbours in the feature space.

- **Random Forest (RF)**: An ensemble of decision trees. Each tree is trained on a random subset of the data (bootstrapping) and considers only a random subset of features at each split. The final prediction is made by aggregating the predictions of all individual trees, thus reducing variance and overfitting.

- **Gradient Boosting (GB)**: A boosting-based ensemble that builds trees sequentially, where each new tree corrects the residuals of the previous ensemble. It uses gradient descent to minimize loss function.

- **Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)**: A highly optimized implementation of gradient boosting. It improves on GB by adding regularization and using advanced techniques to find best tree splits.

By testing this range of models, we comprehensively assess how well each approach captures the structural patterns within our data. Later on, we investigate whether ensemble learners (stacking and voting) outperform those simpler models.

2) *Feature Selection and Engineering*: At a sample space of 81 and feature space of 63, our data is extremely high-dimensional and risks overfitting. To mitigate that and improve generalizability, we evaluated four feature selection and dimensionality reduction strategies, spanning feature engineering, elimination, and selection.

The following four strategies were implemented and evaluated using scikit-learn and pymrmr [15] libraries in python:

- **Principal Component Analysis (PCA)**: An unsupervised dimensionality reduction, feature engineering technique that creates new features from existing ones to maximize variance in the data. We applied PCA to transform the feature space while retaining variance 93-100% depending on model.

- **Filter-Based Feature Selection (SelectKBest)**: A univariate filter method that selects features by evaluating each individual one's statistical properties. We used scikit-learn's `SelectKBest` method using ANOVA F-value as the

scoring function (`f_classif`) which remove all but the k highest scoring features [16].

- **Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE)**: A wrapper algorithm that works by gradually and iteratively eliminating the weaker, unimportant features until a specified number of features is reached. We used base model as the estimator, except for SVM where we used logistic regression. This method selects features based on their actual contribution to the model's performance, making it computationally extensive, but often more effective than other methods. Note that RFE is inapplicable to kNN in the traditional sense.

- **Minimum Redundancy Maximum Relevance (mRMR)**: A multivariate filter method that selects features based on two criteria: maximum relevance; high correlation (mutual information) between features and target variable, and minimum redundancy; low mutual information between features. This creates a subset of features that are both highly informative and non-redundant. There are two variants: MID which selects features that offer the greatest absolute gain in information about the target, and MIQ which selects features that offer the greatest proportional gain in information relative to their redundancy with already selected features [15][17][18]. Through trial, MIQ proved the highest model-agnostic results.

1) *Training and Validation Pipelines*: We implemented a thorough training and validation pipeline on all model and feature selection combinations. This shared methodology was applied consistently across all 24 model instances (6 algorithms \times 4 feature selection methods) to guarantee a fair comparison. The data were randomly divided into training and testing subsets with an 80/20 ratio, the test set maintained for final performance assessment.

The pipeline was as follows, applied over the train split:

- i. Data preprocessing: For algorithms that are sensitive to scale (LR, SVM, kNN), features were standardized within each fold of cross-validation using `StandardScaler`. Tree-based algorithms (RF, GB, XGB) were trained on unscaled data (except for when using PCA, which is sensitive to scale).

- ii. Pipeline: A scikit-learn `Pipeline` object was created for each model and feature combination, it was responsible for running scaling, feature selection, and model training and validation in order. This was done to create a uniform, easy to edit format and to prevent any data leakage from training process into validation set. Meaning that any transformations to the training data did not affect validation or tests sets.

- iii. Hyperparameter tuning: Model hyperparameters and key feature selection methods parameters (like number of features to keep in SelectKBest) were optimized via Grid Search `GridSearchCV`. The scoring metric was chosen to be ROC-AUC (area under the receiver operating characteristic curve) across all model instances.

- iv. Validation strategy: The performance of each hyperparameter combination was evaluated using Repeated Stratified K-Fold Cross-Validation, where the number of folds was eight and the number of repeats 15. The strategy resulted in 120 unique train-validation splits per model.

v. Model Evaluation & Selection: The hyperparameter configuration that yielded the highest mean ROC-AUC across all 120 validation folds was selected as the optimal pipeline. We ended up with a total of 24 unique best-tuned model instances.

The final evaluation was assessed on the test split, which provided a measure of the model’s ability to generalize to unseen data.

2) *Machine Learning Results and Discussions:* Relying solely on accuracy can give a misleading picture of a model’s performance. To get a full picture, we calculated and compared several key metrics: accuracy, F1-score, recall (sensitivity), precision, and Area Under the Curve (AUC).

We primarily used ROC-AUC as our key metric for model comparison. AUC is valuable because it measures the model’s ability to separate the classes across all possible decision thresholds. Table II presents the AUC scores averaged over 120 training folds for our six classifiers using our four different feature selection (FS) strategies.

As shown in Table II, almost all models performed considerably well, with tree-based models (RF and XGB) coming in the lead. XGBoost came as the best performer overall. Paired with RFE, it yielded the highest AUC at 0.943. This implies the existence of strong non-linear relationships between features. The low standard deviations indicate stable and consistent performance across all 120 training folds.

It’s worth noting that there is a considerable age imbalance between HC and PD subjects, which creates an inherent bias. Through initial trials in this study, a SHAP analysis found age to be an extremely discriminating attribute. This variable exhibited dominant influence on model predictions, which is also observed in a study by Sannino et al. [19] where age achieved an InfoGain score of ~0.38, four times higher than the next important features. We argue that including age feature inflates performance metrics and results in a clinically irrelevant model.

Therefore, we reran our models with a discarded age attribute for a comprehensive analysis. The resulting CV AUC scores were as shown in Table III.

The removal of the age feature caused a massive and consistent decrease in AUC scores for every model and every feature selection method. The average AUC drops from ~0.85 to ~0.68, which is barely any better than random guessing. No single model or FS method dominates anymore. Values of standard deviations across all models are much higher (e.g. ± 0.19 , ± 0.21), which indicates increased uncertainty and a less stable performance across training folds.

The inherent problem seems to be a high variance in the data, which means that the audio might not have enough signal to inform strong, decisive features and the noise signal could be overpowering.

The reason why SelectKBest and mRMR generally yielded the best results with the age attribute present is because it identified age as the most relevant feature to the target and selected it. The information the age presented overpowered other signals. This explains why PCA didn’t perform as well with age since its core working is to explain the variance in the data through creating new components, which might not have been as heavily influenced by age as the other FS methods.

With the absence of age bias, simpler, linear models (LR and SVM) maintained a consistently moderate performance, particularly with PCA and mRMR. Those models have higher inductive bias, meaning they make stronger assumptions about the form of underlying data and class distributions. This makes them less prone to overfitting on a certain strong feature, and it indicates a moderate linear signal in the feature set. LR and SVM have a strong preference for simplicity, which is usually advantageous in a noisy environment with no strong signal. Table IV presents the metric scores for those two classifiers, and some other for comparison, on the test set. Note that the test set might be an easier split to some models than others. The performance is notably poor.

TABLE II. COMPARISON BETWEEN CV AUC SCORES OF DIFFERENT MODELS USING FOUR DIFFERENT FS METHODS WITH THE INFLUENCE OF THE AGE ATTRIBUTE

	PCA	SelectKBest	RFE	mRMR
LR	0.862 \pm 0.10	0878 \pm 0.08	0.851 \pm 0.09	0.879 \pm0.09
SVM	0.827 \pm 0.11	0.880 \pm0.09	0.860 \pm 0.10	0.866 \pm 0.09
kNN	0.743 \pm 0.12	0.888 \pm0.10	-	0.819 \pm 0.11
RF	0.808 \pm 0.11	0.919 \pm 0.08	0.919 \pm0.07	0.912 \pm 0.07
GB	0.762 \pm 0.14	0.843 \pm 0.08	0.840 \pm 0.12	0.850 \pm0.10
XGB	0.785 \pm 0.13	0.939 \pm 0.06	0.943 \pm0.06	0.923 \pm 0.07

TABLE III. COMPARISON BETWEEN CV AUC SCORES OF DIFFERENT MODELS USING FOUR DIFFERENT FS METHODS WITHOUT THE INFLUENCE OF THE AGE ATTRIBUTE

	PCA	SelectKBest	RFE	mRMR
LR	0.739 \pm 0.17	0.647 \pm 0.18	0.702 \pm 0.14	0.753 \pm0.18
SVM	0.720 \pm 0.16	0.638 \pm 0.19	0.696 \pm 0.14	0.744 \pm0.19
kNN	0.719 \pm0.19	0.637 \pm 0.21	-	0.675 \pm 0.18
RF	0.680 \pm 0.17	0.685 \pm0.17	0.660 \pm 0.15	0.664 \pm 0.18
GB	0.661 \pm 0.17	0.665 \pm 0.21	0.621 \pm 0.16	0.673 \pm0.21
XGB	0.671 \pm 0.17	0.673 \pm 0.19	0.671 \pm 0.14	0.684 \pm0.18

TABLE IV. METRICS OF TOP PERFORMERS WITHOUT AGE.

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
LR mRMR	0.647	0.651	0.647	0.640
SVM mRMR	0.706	0.707	0.706	0.704
RF SelectKBest	0.765	0.846	0.750	0.742

A contributing factor to this dilemma is the small sample space ($n=81$). Without enough samples that can be further distributed across training and validation, the model might not have what it needs to converge. This could be proven, or disproven, by the use of a bigger dataset which wasn't available to us in the making of the paper.

Fig. 3a is a visualization of the ROC curves for some of the top performers, evaluated on the feature set without age and computed at each of the 120 folds. The curves for all models cluster near the diagonal line of random guessing. This confirms that these models possess limited standalone predictive power for distinguishing PwPD from HC.

Meanwhile Fig. 3b illustrates the ROC curves for these same models under the same conditions, but with age attribute included. The significant upward shift proves that age is a confounding variable that creates a biased model which might misclassify an older healthy patient, or a younger PD patient.

It's worth noting that RF with SelectKBest is essentially RF with no FS since the ideal hyperparameter for k , the number of features, was 'all'.

Note that the feature set we use from hereon would be excluding the age feature.

To get a view on the data we're dealing with, we plotted four different features for analysis with box plots. Fig. 4 shows our resulting plots. We can notice immediately that the features generally have high variance and low inter-class separability, meaning the feature has low signal-to-noise ratio. That means those features are uninformative for our task and it actively harms the model predictions. The fact that some AUC scores like those of the linear models reach moderate values means that we do have signal in the features, but it is overpowered by noise and uninformative attributes.

1) *Ensemble Classifier Models and Results:* The individual models evaluated in the previous section each possess unique inductive biases that make them susceptible to specific types of errors. To investigate the potential for a more robust and generalized predictor, we hypothesized that an ensemble model could balance the strengths of diverse models while mitigating their individual weaknesses.

Fig. 3. Comparison of ROC curves for a select models with and without age attribute

Ensemble learning can be defined as methods that use multiple learning algorithms to obtain a better predictive performance than could be from said algorithms individually [20], provided that they are sufficiently diverse, meaning they make error on different subsets of the data. Fig. 5 presents insight over the errors made by the base models.

To ensure this diversity, we constructed our ensemble from models of different principles: linear models to capture linear decision boundaries, distance-based models to capture complex, non-linear relationships, and tree-based models to capture high-level feature interactions. We decided on the set of 6 classifiers mentioned in the subsection above: LR with PCA, kNN with PCA, SVM with mRMR, XGB with mRMR, RF with SelectKBest, and GB with mRMR. All base models were configured using the optimal hyperparameters identified during prior cross-validation. In this context, base models might be referred to as weak learners.

We implemented three ensemble strategies: Hard Voting Ensemble Classifier (HVEC) for a prediction based on majority rule (most shared prediction across all weak learners), Soft Voting Ensemble Classifier (SVEC) for a probabilistic prediction that utilizes the confidence of each base model in their answer, and Stacked Generalization (Stacking) Classifier to implement a meta-learner to optimally combine base models' predictions.

The performance of all ensemble methods was evaluated with the same 8-fold cross validation, repeated 15 times for a total of 120 training folds. Soft Voting was given the following weights [0.3, 0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 0.1, 0.2] corresponding to the models LR PCA, kNN PCA, SVM mRMR, XGB mRMR, RF SelectKBest, GB mRMR respectively.

The performance of the three strategies is summarized in Table V and Table VI. Contrary to initial hypothesis, the ensemble models, while on the higher side compared to the base models, did not offer a significant improvement. The

Fig. 4. Box plot visualizations of four different features between our two classes

Error Distribution Across Base Classifiers for Parkinson's Disease Detection
(0 = Correct Prediction, FP = False Positive, FN = False Negative)

Test Sample Index	lr_pca	knn_pca	svm_nnmr	xgb_nnmr	rf_selectk	gb_nnmr
0	0	0	0	0	0	FP
1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	FN	0	FN	FN	0
3	0	0	0	0	FN	FN
4	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	FN	0	0	0	0
8	0	FP	FP	0	0	FP
9	FN	FN	FN	FN	FN	FN
10	FP	0	FP	0	0	0
11	0	FP	0	0	0	FP
12	0	0	0	0	0	FP
13	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	0	0	FN	0	FN	0
15	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	0	0	FN	FN	0	FN

Fig. 5. Box plot visualizations of four different features between our two classes

high standard deviation values, indicate that the performance was highly variable and unstable.

As shown in Table VI, Soft Voting ensemble achieved the highest accuracy and the highest cross-validated AUC score. While those metrics are seemingly moderately high, they are consistent with the performance ceiling observed in the best individual models. Models with such instability are clinically unreliable, as its performance would be unpredictable and highly dependent on the specific patient cohort it encounters.

D. Transfer Learning with Pretrained CNN

To address the limitations posed by classical machine learning we turned to deep learning. With a small sample space, normal DL might not be feasible as it is constantly data-hungry. This is where transfer learning fits perfectly, particularly transfer learning with pretrained CNNs. Models such as MobileNet, EfficientNet, and ResNet are trained on large-scale image datasets (e.g. ImageNet) and can transfer their learned feature extraction capabilities to smaller, domain-specific tasks through a process of fine-tuning. This process is best for small datasets that are prone to overfitting. It generalizes the knowledge of image processing for different visual features, which are useful for analysing biomedical spectrograms.

Speech is a time-frequency signal. Transforming audio into spectrograms allows to turn Parkinson's detection into an image classification task. Those spectrograms preserve

TABLE V. MEAN CV AUC OF ENSEMBLES

	Mean CV AU	Std CV AUC
Soft Voting	0.784	±0.247
Hard Voting	0.766	±0.203
Stacking	0.768	±0.255

TABLE VI. COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE ON TEST SET

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Soft Voting	0.824	0.826	0.826	0.824
Hard Voting	0.765	0.846	0.750	0.742
Stacking	0.765	0.780	0.757	0.757

pathological markers. The spectrograms can then be fed into a CNN (or pretrained CNN in our case), trained, tuned, and tested.

1) *Generating the Spectrograms*: We followed the procedure outlined in the paper by Iyer et al. [12], implemented in python using the scipy and librosa libraries. Each ".wav" file was loaded at its native sampling rate and converted into a signal. A Short-Time Fourier Transformation (STFT) was then applied to analyse the frequency of the audio over time. The STFT was computed with a 32ms sliding window, 50% overlap rate between adjacent windows, and a 1024-point Fast Fourier Transform (FFT).

The magnitude spectrum obtained from the STFT was normalized to decibels using [12]:

$$S_{dB}(f, t) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{|S(f, t)|}{\max(|S(f, t)|) + \epsilon} \right)$$

Where $|S(f, t)|$ is the magnitude at the frequency f and time t , and ϵ is a small constant to avoid division by zero. This ensured that spectrograms are on a comparable scale and independent of other noisy variables.

Axes and margins were removed to produce clean, standardized 600×600 pixel images suitable for input to convolutional neural networks. Fig. 6a and 6b are examples of PD sample spectrogram and HC sample spectrogram respectively.

2) *Transfer Learning with MobileNetV2s*: MobileNetV2 is a lightweight CNN, pre-trained on ImageNet [21]. It's deep learning model designed for efficiency on mobile devices. Its architecture is optimized to get high accuracy with less computation, it has smaller

number of parameters as opposed to other counterparts like ResNet or InceptionV3, which makes it ideal for our task.

The spectrograms needed to be resized to 224×224 pixels to comply with input requirements, and normalized to a pixel range of [0,1].

For an input of (244, 244, 3), in which 3 is the RGB channel, MobileNetV2 outputs a 4D feature map of the dimensions (None, 7, 7, 1280). The image is reduced to a 7×7 grid, with 1280 total channels.

To increase the validity of our model and reduce overfitting, careful data augmentation was applied. Transformations were limited to those that wouldn't affect or alter pathological markers and preserve acoustic features while increasing total sample size, and they are as follows: zooming ($\pm 20\%$), horizontal and vertical shifts ($\pm 10\%$), brightness scaling, horizontal flips.

The convolutional base of MobileNetV2 was initialized with pretrained ImageNet weights. Early CNN layers were frozen to prevent their weights from updating during training, preserving capabilities of ImageNet. The original

Fig. 6. Spectrogram sample examples

classification head was replaced with a custom head better fit for our use case. This new head consisted of a Global Average Pooling layer which reduces dimensionality, a Batch Normalization layer that transforms data and standardizes it, a Dropout layer of 0.6 to prevent depending on a certain feature and prevents overfitting, which is the most crucial in our case thus the high value. After that comes a Dense layer which is basically the learner in this model, it looks for non-linear combinations of the 1280 features that are most determinant in distinguishing the two classes. This layer is regularized with L2 and followed with another Dropout layer of rate 0.5 then another Dense layer which is the final “decision maker” layer that uses *softmax* activation function. Fig. 7 describes the format of the custom head.

The model was compiled with Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.00005 and trained using cross-entropy loss, which is the standard scoring rule for classification tasks. Both accuracy and AUC metrics were calculated at each epoch.

The training procedure included early stopping through monitoring validation AUC values with a patience of 10 epochs. It also utilizes learning rate reduction by half (factor=0.5) on plateau with a patience of 5 epochs. Meaning it checks if the validation loss has decreased compared to the lowest value so far. If it didn't for 5 epochs in a row, then the learning rate is halved for the upcoming epochs.

The data was divided into 70% training, 10% validation, and 20% test sets. The procedure was repeated for 25 independent runs, each with a different random seed for data splitting. A total of 50 epochs per run was chosen, with 15 steps per epoch. Those 25 runs were executed a total of 7 times resulting in a total of 175 model trains.

The mean test AUC across the 25 runs was 0.71 ± 0.08 , with the best model achieving a ROC-AUC of .0.896. A total of 14 runs out of 25 achieved a test AUC above 0.70. Fig. 8 presents the learning and loss curves of one of the runs.

These results demonstrate a critical improvement at detecting discriminative features in speech from other tested models and architectures.

Fig. 7. Layers of the custom MobileNetV2 head

Fig. 8. Learning accuracy and loss plot for run 7

III. CONCLUSION

We aimed through this study to compare methods for detecting Parkinson’s disease through voice and to examine the assumptions behind their reported successes. Several important conclusions can be drawn.

First, our experiments confirm that demographic imbalance, particularly in age differences between Parkinson’s and healthy participants, remains the single largest confounder in voice-based machine learning for PD when age is included in the training. This fundamentally contradicts the premise of using voice as a disease-specific biomarker, yet several reviewed studies included age as a feature. Doing so undermines the clinical relevance of their models, as the sharp decline in performance when age was excluded indicates that many reported results may be capturing population dynamics rather than pathology. Along with the discussed concerns of data leakage. This raises a broader concern in biomedical AI: high cross-validation scores do not equate to clinical usefulness when models learn to recognize shortcuts or easily learned cues instead of true pathological markers.

Second, the inconsistency of ensemble learners shows that more complexity does not always mean better or more reliable performance on small, noisy datasets. While ensembles are praised for improved robustness, our results indicate that in small, heterogeneous biomedical datasets their apparent benefits can be inconsistent. High fold-to-fold variability and low diversity among base models may produce validation improvements that fail to generalize.

Third, our results with transfer learning indicate that pretrained CNNs can partially address the drawbacks of handcrafted acoustic features, even with small sample sizes. By turning voice into an image classification task, MobileNetV2 achieved significantly better discriminative ability than traditional methods. This suggests that speech pathology leaves subtle but noticeable traces in spectrotemporal patterns. However, the wide variation across runs also shows that transfer learning alone is not enough without strategies to stabilize training, increase data diversity, and ensure interpretability.

Finally, this study emphasizes the need for clear benchmarking frameworks. Ultimately, it is thorough methodology, rather than model complexity, that will

determine whether voice-based AI can achieve genuine clinical value.

IV. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This study is subject to several limitations. Most notably the small dataset size ($n=81$) and demographic imbalance, particularly in age. Furthermore, the acoustic features exhibited high variance and low inter-class separability, leading to poor predictive signal and instability in both classical and ensemble models. The reliance on a single dataset also prevented external validation, restricting the scope of conclusions that can be drawn about clinical applicability.

Future work should focus on addressing these limitations through larger and more demographically balanced datasets, which would provide more reliable training and validation conditions. Incorporating multimodal data, such as combining voice with other non-invasive biomarkers like handwriting or gait like done by Vasquez-Correa et al. [6], could further improve robustness and sensitivity.

From a methodological standpoint, recent studies employing advanced deep learning architectures, including EfficientNet, attention-based models, or hybrid approaches that integrate temporal and spectral information have reported notable improvements. Their effectiveness, however, remains difficult to validate. A paper published by Tabashum et al. states that despite the large number of studies published every year, very few ML systems have been adopted for real-world use [22]. This same paper goes into details over limitations of current research like lack of external validation or limited interpretability, which aligns with our own findings.

This work is best viewed as a systematic case study for methodological comparison, rather than a framework intended for immediate clinical deployment.

V. DATA AND CODE AVAILABILITY

The data supporting the findings of this study are openly available in Figshare at https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Voice_Samples_for_Patients_with_Parkinson_s_Disease_and_Healthy_Controls/23849127

The software implementation and code scripts developed for this project are made publicly available. The repository includes configuration files for OpenSMILE used in GeMAPS feature extraction, Python scripts implementations of all used ML models, along with feature selection, spectrogram generation scripts, and the MobileNetV2 implementation and final model. The repository can be accessed at https://github.com/meiuxx/Parkinson_Speech_Detection and is distributed under the MIT License.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the Faculty of Information and Communication Technology Engineering at Tartous University. The authors extend their gratitude to Professor Jaafar Salman, Reem Mhanna, and Samah Suleiman for

their constructive supervision and guidance throughout the development of this project.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The individual contributions of the authors are as follows, described according to CRediT taxonomy: M.B.: Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation (core experiments), Methodology design, Software (primary implementation and final code), Visualization, and Writing (Original Draft Preparation). M.A.: Conceptualization, Investigation (literature review for deep learning), Software (initial framework and library testing for Transfer Learning), and Writing (Review & Editing). S.A.: Software (library testing for Transfer Learning), Resources (reference gathering), Investigation (supporting literature review), Validation, and Writing (Review & Editing). All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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